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ESIRA – ENHANCING SOCIAL INNOVATION IN RURAL AREAS

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MAPS ROADMAPS: CONTEXT, GOVERNANCE, OPERATION AND MAP'S OBJECTIVES

Deliverable D5.1

WP5 – Community-led innovation spaces and pilot social economy initiatives

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List of acronyms

Acronyms	Full name
CoP	Community of Practice
EEC	European Economic Community.
ESIRA	Enhancing Social Innovation in Rural Areas.
FTC	Federazione Trentina della Cooperazione.
LAG	Local Action Group.
MAP / MAPs	Multi-Actor Platform (s)
NEET	Not in Education, Employment or Training.
NGOs	Non-governmental Organisations
SGEIs	Services of General Economic Interest.
TBD	To Be Determined.

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1. Executive Summary

This Deliverable 5.1, "MAPs Roadmaps: Context, Governance, Operation, and MAP's Objectives", provides the required guidelines and recommendations for developing appropriate MAP governance policies and facilitating the implementation of the ESIRA project's phases over four years. MAPs' roadmaps aim to foster collaborative governance within MAPs and support the long-term sustainability of these social structures.

The Deliverable first gathers the characteristics of the different MAPs constituted by the consortium members, providing a comprehensive but summarised perspective of their characteristics to achieve this goal. Additionally, it compiles guidance on managing MAP meetings and communication, considers the possibility of creating different working groups, suggests potential training actions, and outlines the objectives to be achieved by these MAPs.

This document also emphasises the importance of stakeholder engagement and collaborative decision-making processes within the MAP framework. It provides strategies for fostering inclusive participation from all relevant actors, ensuring the governance model is transparent and democratic. The deliverable also outlines the required efforts and targeted measures to ensure that vulnerable individuals and groups in pilot areas are effectively reached, engaged, and benefited by the project, highlighting the importance of aligning MAP objectives with broader regional and national social innovation goals and enhancing the impact and sustainability of the initiatives undertaken.

2. Introduction

2.1. Objective of the deliverable

The EU-funded ESIRA project, Enhancing Social Innovation in Rural Areas, plays a crucial role in meeting the needs of rural areas, particularly marginalised communities, through a place-based innovation approach that establishes Multi-Actor Platforms (MAPs) and runs Rural Labs. The main objective of the ESIRA project is to promote innovative social economy initiatives in rural areas to address the gap between existing social economy initiatives and policies and effectively support and engage vulnerable groups. Although regional differences exist, vulnerable groups in rural areas commonly include women, young people, older adults, retired people, migrants, ethnic minorities, and persons with disabilities. These populations are particularly exposed to heightened risks of poverty, social exclusion, and limited access to essential services. Thus, the project will research community-led rural innovation spaces, pilot social economy initiatives, and formulate recommendations for policymakers.

To do this, a specific objective of ESIRA is to design and test a flexible enabling framework for the upscale of social economy through community-led innovation spaces and specific policy architectures that break current silos. Rural communities need to benefit from improved enabling environments in the form of place-based, community-led innovation ecosystems that can guarantee access to physical and digital infrastructure and services, improved access to knowledge, advice and business development support, cooperation and networking, access to finance and guidance to thrive in a complex puzzle of different legislative instruments. The social economy includes organisations that aim to benefit either their members or the community in which they operate. Social economy organisations are designed to enable the active participation of a multiplicity of stakeholders, representing different components of society. ESIRA recognises the added value of social economy organisations and undertakes to facilitate an innovative framework to support vulnerable groups in rural areas through Multi-Actor Platforms (MAPs). MAPs will be designed as community-led spaces that nurture social innovation and reinforce the systemic levers for social economy initiatives, building on previous best practices and advancing effective mechanisms for self-governance and support.

Throughout the project, **MAPs have to be able to 1) facilitate social innovations, 2) establish Rural Labs, and 3) pilot social economy initiatives.**

Work Package 5 (WP5), Community-led innovation spaces and pilot social economy initiatives, has to implement and operate the MAPs, following the guidelines of Work Package 3 (WP3), Framework setting for Multi-Actor Platforms operating as community-led innovation spaces. During the first months of the ESIRA project, these two work packages have collaborated to develop a common methodology for setting up and operating the regional MAPs in the selected rural territories. WP3 transferred the MAP methodology and guidelines to WP5 to facilitate MAP establishment.

As a result of the WP3 and WP5 collaboration, this deliverable presents the roadmaps of the MAPs established within the ESIRA project. These roadmaps are designed to guide the collaborative work of each MAP by defining shared objectives, roles, responsibilities, and an implementation timeline, to ensure both participatory and effective functioning of ESIRA MAPs and to build the appropriate local framework for the development of the Rural Labs, which will identify, support, and promote innovative social economy initiatives in each pilot area. In seeking to synthesise and distinguish between the two concepts, from the ESIRA perspective, it is considered that MAPs are about coordination and influence; it means that these structures create a coherent environment for multiple stakeholders to align strategies and scale impact. On the other hand, Rural Labs are about innovation and experimentation: they empower communities to design and test solutions tailored to their local realities

2.2. Deliverable structure

The deliverable is structured into four main sections. The structure presented below guides the reader through the logical sequence of the deliverable, from the contextual overview of the MAPs to the governance and operational framework, and finally to the development and presentation of the MAPs' roadmap. First, the objective and structure of this deliverable are presented, and the following epigraph introduces the methodological approach used in the ESIRA project, including the MAPs roadmaps, to understand the interaction and complementarity of MAPs and Rural Labs. The second section provides an overview of the MAPs established within ESIRA and introduces their key characteristics. The third section presents the governance and operational framework that guides the functioning of the MAPs, including regulations and internal organisation, the principles of democratic governance, the roles of MAP members, meetings, communication, and training and capacity-building activities. The fourth section presents the roadmaps themselves, detailing the objectives, phases, actions, and milestones that will guide the work of each MAP throughout the project.

2.3. Methodological approach for roadmap definition

ESIRA's Multi-actor approach rests on **three key pillars** to engage diverse groups, based on the "Quadruple Helix" (civil society, policy, business, and academia): **Multi-Actor Platforms (MAPs), Rural Labs, and Community of Practice (CoP)**. This approach helps solve complex problems, as diverse expertise and experiences are represented within the MAPs, Rural Labs mentors, and CoP participants (see Figure 1). As a result of this knowledge and practical expertise exchange, MAPs must be capable of facilitating the development of social economy innovations through the active and collaborative participation of different stakeholders linked to the territory, becoming the decision-making body in the implementation of Rural Labs and involving vulnerable groups throughout the process.

This methodological approach provides the foundations for an innovative co-creation process based on local needs, enabling the identification and support of social economy initiatives. In the first months of the ESIRA Project (M1-M6), the nine MAPs have been established to operate in the nine pilot zones. Each of them has followed a different engagement process to reach the most relevant rural actors, adopting a flexible structure, deciding on the topics to be addressed, and selecting the social economy initiatives to be supported throughout the project in the Rural Labs.

MAP definition

MAP in the ESIRA project is **a flexible platform composed of people linked to the pilot rural areas**, participating either individually or on behalf of institutions (civil society, policy, business and academic). The participants are active in collaboration and come together to co-define challenges and co-create solutions with the common goal of achieving inclusive rural development through innovative social economy initiatives. **MAP is the decision-making body in the pilot guided by MAP facilitators**, which meets and works collaboratively, participatively, and democratically. MAP will identify the innovative social economy initiatives to be supported by ESIRA through promoters' ideas or MAP consensus. MAP is a flexible structure that allows members to join or leave as their availability and individual commitment change.

The individuals who become MAP members possess the power and legitimacy of their group when representing them, as well as a sense of need and urgency to act and advance social innovations in the rural areas of their MAP area. The inclusion of diverse groups of actors ensures a range of perspectives and experiences, which can help achieve more elaborate, out-of-the-box results. MAP members must be carefully selected to achieve optimal MAP activity within the key stakeholder groups identified in the MAP area in relation to social innovations. The invited actors must represent not only all quadruple helix axes but also all **vulnerable groups** within the MAP structure, including their leading representative organisations. As representatives of the rural community who combine diverse sources of knowledge, experience, and motivation, **MAPs have the potential to initiate change in rural areas** by analysing the context, identifying challenges and opportunities, and seeking new solutions.

Rural Lab definition

As mentioned above, the **Rural Lab is an open space for co-creation, innovation and experimentation of new social economy initiatives**. It takes the form of working sessions in which initiatives' promoters and MAP members, with the support of other stakeholders who might not be directly in the MAP (experts, collaborators, etc.), will work to ensure that the ideas generated in the MAP incorporate a social dimension that aligns them with the objectives of the ESIRA project and becomes them into genuine social innovations for rural communities. It serves as a living laboratory where innovative solutions are shaped to promote economic, social, and environmental sustainability in

rural areas. Rural Lab is articulated to the identification, development and support of social economy initiatives.

Community of Practice (CoP) definition

By contrast, a **Community of Practice (CoP)** is a group of people who “share a concern or a passion for something they do and learn how to do it better as they interact regularly” (Wenger-Trayner & Wenger-Trayner, 2015). Indeed, it constitutes a collective learning network in which individuals who share a common interest engage in sustained interaction. Through the exchange of knowledge, reflective dialogue, and the dissemination of best practices, members of a CoP cultivate shared expertise and improved professional practices, thereby reinforcing both individual competencies and collective capacity within the field. Taking this definition, the ESIRA Community of Practice (CoP) is a group of academics, professionals, rural entrepreneurs, students, MAP members, managers and facilitators, politicians, rural actors and inhabitants, that voluntarily engage in collective learning to improve their skills and knowledge in rural issues, development, opportunities, challenges and vulnerabilities, including the social problem of social exclusion in rural areas. ESIRA CoP will contribute to developing collective and specialised knowledge through the exchange of experiences, ideas, and best practices among its members, experts from different backgrounds, to innovate, solve problems, generate new knowledge, promote improvements and solutions, improve skills, and strengthen knowledge in the MAP and in the Rural Lab sessions. ESIRA CoP is structured to meet in person (local groups) and online (international group).

Figure 1 MAP, Rural Lab, and CoP interaction

DECISION-MAKING

Who:
Local actors

What:
They make proposals and decisions for the project

How:
Meetings and work sessions of the MAP

CO-CREATION

Who:
Initiative promoters

What:
They build innovative projects

How:
Workgroups, co-design, and co-creation

Who: Experts, local technicians, academics, professionals, and traditional knowledge holders.

What: They share and create collective knowledge.

How: Experiences, success stories, best practices, networks and alliances, new solutions.

SHARING

Source: Own elaboration

3. Overview of ESIRA Multi-Actor Platforms and their Characteristics

Below is a description of the **nine MAPs established in the ESIRA project**, along with the rural area's territorial, social, and economic conditions. In each MAP and rural location, a different engagement process has been carried out to reach the most relevant actors and stakeholder groups, and to ensure the participation of vulnerable groups. For each MAP, a table is compiled with the following information: **MAP dimension** (location, size, number of municipalities, number of inhabitants, language, economic activity sectors, and main vulnerable groups identified), **MAP actors** (number of MAP members, facilitator role and monitor role), **representativeness and participation** of different groups and actors (women, people over 65, people under 30, public institutions, local businesses and entrepreneurs, members of the cultural sector and creative industries, members of environmental associations, members born in foreign countries, members belonging to ethnic minorities, and others), and **working groups**, if any have been created.

3.1. MAP's description and rationale for selecting the pilot areas

3.1.1. Jablanica and Pcinja MAP (Serbia)

Jablanica and Pcinja Districts are in the southeastern part of the Republic of Serbia, in the central region of the southern Balkans. This region borders the Nisava, Toplica, and Pirot districts to the north, Bulgaria to the east, North Macedonia to the south, and the Autonomous Province of Kosovo and Metohija to the west. According to the 2022 census, the territory of these districts comprises 699 settlements with 380,000 inhabitants, accounting for 6% of the total population of Serbia.

During April, May, and June, a series of initial engagements were conducted with key local stakeholders in the Jablanica and Pcinja Districts. Stakeholders convened for the general presentation of the Multi-Actor Platform (MAP) in the City of Leskovac, hosted at the Center for Development of Jablanica and Pcinja Districts, key stakeholders. Moreover, 4 comprehensive presentations took place across the six local municipalities within the districts. These sessions featured presentations and exchanges of ideas focused on optimising the operations of the MAP, integrating local initiatives, and establishing foundational sustainability networks aimed at nurturing innovative initiatives.

The name “**Mreža za Lokalni Inkluzivni i Inovativni Ekonomski razvoj**” (“Network for Inclusive and Innovative Local Economic Development”) was chosen to reflect the core objectives and principles of the initiative:

- **Inclusive:** Emphasizes the importance of involving and benefiting all segments of the local community, ensuring that economic development initiatives are accessible and beneficial to everyone, including marginalized groups.
- **Innovative:** Highlights the need for creative and forward-thinking approaches in fostering economic growth within the region, aiming to introduce new ideas, technologies, and practices that can enhance local competitiveness.
- **Local:** Indicates a focus on initiatives explicitly tailored to the needs and context of the Jablanica and Pcinja District, recognising the unique challenges and opportunities present in the local environment.
- **Economic Development:** Clearly states the overarching goal of promoting economic growth, job creation, and sustainable development within the region, aiming to improve living standards and quality of life for residents.

By combining these elements, the name conveys a commitment to inclusive economic growth through innovative local strategies, ultimately aiming to create a more prosperous and resilient community in the Jablanica and Pcinja District.

Table 1 Jablanica and Pcinja MAP characteristics (M6)

MAP DIMENSION	DESCRIPTION AND DATA
Geographical location	Jablanica and Pcinja Districts are in the southeastern part of the Republic of Serbia, in the central region of the southern Balkans. This region borders the Nisava, Toplica, and Pirot districts to the north, Bulgaria to the east, North Macedonia to the south, and the Autonomous Province of Kosovo and Metohija to the west.
Extension in Km2	6,289 km ²
Number of municipalities (total)	13 municipalities
Number of inhabitants (total)	380,000 inhabitants
Language	Serbian, Albanian, Bulgarian, Roma
Main sectors of economic activity	All municipalities except Vranje (region 2 - Region of Small Urban Economies with Intensive Agriculture) in Jablanica and Pcinja District belong to the third region - the Mountainous region, with an economy based on natural resources, which is also the largest territorial

	region in the Republic of Serbia (29% of the territory). They are characterised by diversified economic and agricultural production, with potential for tourism.
Main vulnerable groups	Women, young entrepreneurs, youth in NEET position
MAP ACTORS	DESCRIPTION AND DATA
Number of members of the MAP (total)	25 members
MAP facilitator	Nebojsa Novković, ESIRA project manager and primary personnel for implementing strategic activities of the local MAP, coordinating with the established team.
MAP monitor	Marina Andelković, Communication Manager of the ESIRA project and the person responsible for all related logistical activities
MAP ACTORS' REPRESENTATION	DESCRIPTION AND DATA (total number)
Female participants	16 (64%)
Members in the age 65+	0 (0%)
Members in the age 30-	10 (40%)
Public Institution members	13 (52%)
Local enterprises/entrepreneurs' members by economic sector	5 (25%)
Cultural and creative sector members	4 (16%)
Environmental associations members	2 (8%)

Members born in a foreign country	0 (0%)
Ethnic minority members	5 (25%)
Other	0 (0%)
MAP WORKING GROUPS	NUMBER OF PEOPLE IN THE GROUP
Coordination	11
Retraining programs	5
Entrepreneurship	5
Social inclusion	5

3.1.2. Innlandet MAP (Norway)

The Kongsvinger region is in the southern part of Innlandet County and is situated close to the Swedish border. It comprises six municipalities: Kongsvinger, Eidskog, Sør-Odal, Nord-Odal, Grue, and Åsnes. Kongsvinger serves as the central hub for the region. As of the first quarter of 2024, the population of the Kongsvinger region was 49 073.

Like other parts of Innlandet county, this region experiences very small population growth and would have depopulated had it not been for immigrants. The Kongsvinger region has a high share of older people, a decreasing share of young people and people of working age, and a relatively low share of people with higher education compared to the Norwegian average. At the same time, it is a region known for its openness to innovation and has been home to many exciting projects focused on innovation and inclusion.

Table 2 Innlandet MAP characteristics (M6)

MAP DIMENSION	DESCRIPTION AND DATA
Geographical location	The Norwegian MAP is situated in the Kongsvinger region, in Innlandet county.
Extension in Km2	4 969 km ²
Number of municipalities (total)	In the Kongsvinger region: 6 municipalities
Number of inhabitants (total)	In the Kongsvinger region: 49,073 inhabitants

Language	Norwegian
Main sectors of economic activity	Agriculture stands for almost ¼ of all registered businesses in the region, but if we look at businesses with employees, retail is the biggest sector. The industry in the region is rather diverse, with metal and mechanical Industry, forestry and wood industry, electronics and technology, bioenergy and environmental technology, as well as the construction sector.
Main vulnerable groups	For the Kongsvinger region MAP we are focusing on people with disabilities.
MAP ACTORS	DESCRIPTION AND DATA
Number of members of the MAP (total)	12 members. We are still recruiting for the MAP.
MAP facilitator	Lisa Knatterud Wold, Inland Norway University of Applied Sciences, lisa.wold@inn.no
MAP monitor	Berit Kvaløy, Innlandet County Council, berkvl@innlandetfylke.no
MAP ACTORS' REPRESENTATION	DESCRIPTION AND DATA (total number)
Female participants	7 members (58,34%)
Male participants	5 members (41,67%)
Members in the age 65+	1 member (8,34%)
Members in the age 30-	1 member (8,34%)
Vulnerable groups (People with disabilities)	4 members (33,34%)
Public Institution members	2 members (16,67%)

Civil society organisations	3 members (25%)
Academia/Science	1 member (8,34%)
Business	3 members (25%)
Policy	4 members (33,34%)

3.1.3. Leski-Bieszczadzki MAP (Poland)

The Leski-Bieszczadzki MAP, located in a deeply rural mountainous area between the Leski and Bieszczadzki poviats in southeastern Poland, spans 1,974 km² and borders Ukraine and Slovakia. The wood-related industry, tourism-related services, public services, and other service sectors primarily drive the region's economy. More detailed information is provided in the following table.

Table 3 Leski-Bieszczadzki MAP characteristics (M6)

MAP DIMENSION	DESCRIPTION AND DATA
Geographical location	Leski-Bieszczadzki MAP is a deep rural mountainous area between the Leski and Bieszczadzki poviats in southeastern Poland, near the Polish borders with Ukraine and Slovakia.
Extension in Km2	Total: 1,974 Km2 Leski: 835 km2, Bieszczadzki: 1,139 km2 Source: GUS, 31.XII.2023
Number of municipalities (total)	8
Number of inhabitants (total)	Total: 46,216 habitants [Leski: 25,514, Bieszczadzki: 20,702] Source: GUS, 31.XII.2023
Language	Polish

Main sectors of economic activity	Wood-related industry, tourism-related services, public services and other services
Main vulnerable groups	Older people, migrants, women, people with disabilities, youth
MAP ACTORS	DESCRIPTION AND DATA
Number of members of the MAP (total)	20
MAP facilitator	Katarzyna Gizińska, ERDN researcher katarzyna.gizinska@erdn.eu
MAP monitor	Iwona Woch, LAG Zielone Bieszczady iwonawoch@tlen.pl
MAP ACTORS' REPRESENTATION	DESCRIPTION AND DATA (total number)
Female participants	12 (60%)
Members in the age 65+	1 (5%)
Members in the age 30-	3 (15%)
Public Institution members	4 (20%)
Local enterprises/entrepreneurs' members by economic sector	15 (75%)
Cultural and creative sector members	7 (35%)
Environmental associations members	0 (0%)
Members born in a foreign country	0 (0%)
Ethnic minority members	0 (0%)

Other	0 (0%)
MAP WORKING GROUPS	NUMBER OF PEOPLE IN THE GROUP
	Regarding the Polish MAP, we do not see the need to create special working groups. If it is needed, we will make it.

3.1.4. Pinares Burgos-Soria MAP (Spain)

The Pinares Burgos-Soria region, encompassing over 100 municipalities, faces significant rural challenges like population ageing and youth migration due to a lack of essential services such as healthcare, transportation, and education. Despite this, locals are initiating cultural, business, and social projects to revitalise the area, with a growing trend of people returning to the village for a slower pace. The region's abundant natural resources, including mountains, pine forests, and fields, offer opportunities for active tourism, local product companies, worker cooperatives, and community associations.

Given the large area of the Pinares Burgos-Soria region, the MAP can adopt a wide range of approaches. One possibility is the creation of cooperatives to represent significant rural sectors, helping to organise and improve their work, market representation, and commercial networks. These could include farmers' cooperatives, wood cooperatives, and cooperatives for entrepreneurial women and youth.

Table 4 Pinares Burgos-Soria MAP characteristics (M6)

MAP DIMENSION	DESCRIPTION AND DATA
Geographical location	Pinares MAP is a deep rural mountainous area between the provinces of Burgos and Soria in Mid-Northern Spain.
Extension in Km2	2,750 Km2
Number of municipalities (total)	100 municipalities.

Number of inhabitants (total)	18,000 inhabitants.
Language	Spanish.
Main sectors of economic activity	Wood-related industry (municipalities own 80% of the total forest area as communal property), cultural and natural tourism.
Main vulnerable groups	Elder people, migrants, women, and people with mental health-related problems.
MAP ACTORS	DESCRIPTION AND DATA
Number of members of the MAP (total)	52 people.
MAP facilitator	Luis Marcos (UBU researcher). Currently looking for a facilitator based in the Pinares area and involved in community-led initiatives.
MAP monitor	Sonia Marcos (UBU researcher). Currently looking for a monitor based in the Pinares area and involved in community-led initiatives.
MAP ACTORS' REPRESENTATION	DESCRIPTION AND DATA (total number)
Female participants	25
Members in the age 65+	30
Members in the age 30-	3
Public Institution members	6
Local enterprises/entrepreneurs' members by economic sector	12

Cultural and creative sector members	TBD
Environmental associations members	TBD
Members born in a foreign country	TBD
Ethnic minority members	TBD
Other	TBD
MAP WORKING GROUPS	NUMBER OF PEOPLE IN THE GROUP
Entrepreneurship	TBD
Transport	TBD
Cultural	TBD
Other	TBD

3.1.5. Abruzzo MAP (Italy)

Abruzzo, a central-southern Italian region, has a population of 1,293,941 (2020) and a density of 119 inhabitants per km² across its 10,831 km², 65% of which is mountainous. L'Aquila, the capital, has 69,900 residents, while Pescara is the largest city with 119,500 inhabitants. The population declined by 3% from 2014 to 2020.

Two-thirds of Abruzzo's municipalities are in inland areas, where one-third of the population lives. The region features 140 libraries and 110 museums, predominantly in inland areas. It also has significant protected areas, including Natura 2000 sites. In 2020, inland areas recorded 472,532 arrivals and 1,659,223 accommodation stays.

Abruzzo hosts 38 community cooperatives across its four provinces, each with unique attributes such as maturity, local engagement, and relationships with public administration. Exemplary cooperatives, such as those in Aielli and Calascio, highlight the cultural richness of the region, while Campo di Giove and San Vincenzo Valle Roveto focus on sustainable food chains and community emporiums.

The Borghi in Rete network, comprising over 30 villages, addresses depopulation through community-based cooperatives that foster sustainable economic activities and active

resident participation. These cooperatives align with the principles of the 2030 Agenda on Sustainability, the Faro Convention, and the Habitat Charter.

Table 5 Abruzzo MAP characteristics (M6)

MAP DIMENSION	DESCRIPTION AND DATA
<p>Geographical location</p>	<p>The province of Chieti is in the Abruzzo region of Italy. It is the easternmost province in the region and is bounded to the northeast by the Adriatic Sea.</p>
<p>Extension in Km2</p>	<p>The province spans an area of approximately 2,599.58 square kilometres.</p>
<p>Number of municipalities (total)</p>	<p>The province of Chieti is divided into 104 municipalities</p>
<p>Number of inhabitants (total)</p>	<p>As of 2017, the province has a total population of approximately 387,649 inhabitants.</p>
<p>Language</p>	<p>The main language spoken in the province of Chieti is Italian, with local dialects influenced by the Abruzzese dialect.</p>
<p>Main sectors of economic activity</p>	<p>The economy of the province of Chieti is supported by industry, services, and tourism. Agriculture, once the primary economic resource, has undergone significant downsizing but still offers various high-</p>

	quality products. The region has also developed innovation processes that have attracted large companies and multinationals
Main vulnerable groups	Older people, migrants.
MAP ACTORS	DESCRIPTION AND DATA
Number of members of the MAP (total)	17
MAP facilitator	Borghi In Rete: info@borghiinrete.it
MAP monitor	<p>Euricse, because of the research activities it conducts at both national/regional and international levels and its expertise in the social economy field.</p> <p>Contact: jacopo.sforzi@euricse.eu</p>
MAP ACTORS' REPRESENTATION	DESCRIPTION AND DATA (total number)
Female participants	10
Members in the age 65+	1
Members in the age 30-	2
Public Institution members	TBD
Local enterprises/entrepreneurs' members by economic sector	12
Cultural and creative sector members	TBD
Environmental associations members	TBD
Members born in a foreign country	TBD
Ethnic minority members	TBD

Other	TBD
MAP WORKING GROUPS	NUMBER OF PEOPLE IN THE GROUP
Entrepreneurship	TBD
Transport	TBD
Cultural	TBD
Other	TBD

3.1.6. Trento MAP (Italy)

The second Italian pilot will be implemented in the Trentino region, located northeast of Italy, corresponding to the Autonomous Province of Trento. Covering an area of over 6,000 km² with a population of 542,996, Trentino is an Alpine, predominantly rural region with 166 small municipalities, most having 500 - 1,000 inhabitants. The main urban centres are Trento (120,000 inhabitants) and Rovereto (40,000 inhabitants). Over 70% of the territory is above 1,000 meters above sea level, and approximately 67% is forested. The entire region is classified as a mountainous disadvantaged area under EEC Directive 268/75 and Legislative Decree IT 146/97.

Regarding to the MAP constitution process, initial contacts with relevant actors in the Trentino pilot have been facilitated by the Federazione Trentina della Cooperazione (FTC) through past and ongoing projects on rural development and community support. Face-to-face meetings were organised with FTC's internal contacts responsible for creating and promoting community spaces and managing Services of General Economic Interest (SGEIs). To enhance these projects and design new socio-economic inclusion opportunities for target groups in the ESIRA project, FTC engaged partners involved in these initiatives and public institutions responsible for services aimed at young women, NEETs, and persons with disabilities.

Through telephone communications and online meetings, ESIRA's objectives and community engagement methods were explained to identify the causes of socio-economic exclusion. FTC also communicated with presidents and directors of consumer cooperative shops and cooperative credit institutions involved in relevant projects to gather their availability and proposals for engaging target actors in the MAPs.

Two public presentations are scheduled for July 8th and 9th to kick off the MAPs, with events hosted in MAP Alta Valsugana and MAP Vallagarina territories. Each presentation will include a 30-minute overview of the ESIRA project and MAPs, a one-hour participative workshop to explore local needs and resources, and a 30-minute snack break for informal discussions. The structure of future MAP meetings will be tailored to the number of members and the topics and activities necessary to make the MAPs operational.

Table 6 Trento MAP characteristics (M6)

MAP DIMENSION	DESCRIPTION AND DATA
Geographical location	<p>The MAP is located in the southern area of the Autonomous Province of Trento/Trentino region. Its borders correspond to those of the Valley Community of Vallagarina, which is bordered to the west by the Valley Community of Alto Garda and Ledro, to the north by the Territory of Val d'Adige, the Valley Community of Valle dei Laghi and the Valley Community of Alta Valsugana and Bersntol, to the east by the Magnifica Comunità degli Altipiani Cimbri and the Province of Vicenza (Veneto region), and to the south by the Province of Verona (Veneto region).</p>
Extension in Km2	622.63 Km2
Number of municipalities (total)	17 municipalities
Number of inhabitants (total)	91,000 inhabitants
Language	Italian
Main sectors of economic activity	The main economic activities that contribute to the development and welfare of MAP are:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Agriculture: The community is known for its wine production (especially Marzemino and Moscato Giallo). In addition, the cultivation of apples is widespread. - Industry: The Vallagarina is home to various industries, including paper production, mechanical engineering, and the food industry. - Tourism: The scenic beauty of the valley, with its mountains and vineyards, attracts many tourists. Tourist activities include hiking, cycling, cultural visits and wine tasting.
Main vulnerable groups	<p>Young women.</p> <p>People in NEET situations.</p> <p>People with disabilities.</p>
MAP ACTORS	DESCRIPTION AND DATA
Number of members of the MAP (total)	27
MAP facilitator	<p>FTC, due to the widespread presence of the Federation's member cooperatives in the territory.</p> <p>Contact: internazionale@ftcoop.it</p>
MAP monitor	<p>Euricse, because of the research activities it carries out at both national/regional and international level and its expertise in the social economy field.</p> <p>Contact: jacopo.sforzi@euricse.eu</p>
MAP ACTORS' REPRESENTATION	DESCRIPTION AND DATA (total number)

Female participants	15
Members in the age 65+	TBD
Members in the age 30-	TBD
Public Institution members	3
Local enterprises/entrepreneurs' members by economic sector	6
Cultural and creative sector members	TBD
Environmental associations members	TBD
Members born in a foreign country	TBD
Ethnic minority members	TBD
Other	TBD
MAP WORKING GROUPS	NUMBER OF PEOPLE IN THE GROUP
Entrepreneurship	TBD
Transport	TBD
Cultural	TBD
Other	TBD

3.1.7. Zachodniopomorskie MAP (Poland)

MAP Zachodniopomorski is situated within Gryfice powiat in north-western Poland, bordered to the north by the Baltic Sea. The district encompasses six municipalities: Gryfice, Płoty, Trzebiatów, Brojce, Karnice, and Rewal. Among these, Rewal and Trzebiatów are known as tourist communes due to their coastal locations, while Gryfice, Brojce, Karnice, and Płoty historically focused on agriculture, with large areas formerly operated by state-owned farms.

The district covers an expansive 1 021 km² and supports a population of approximately 57 000 inhabitants, resulting in a population density of 56 persons per square kilometre. Economic activities in Zachodniopomorski are primarily driven by trade, services, industry, construction, agriculture, and tourism, predominantly within the private sector.

Table 7 Zachodniopomorski MAP characteristics (M6)

MAP DIMENSION	DESCRIPTION AND DATA
Geographical location	MAP Zachodniopomorski is in Gryfice powiat. The district is in north-western Poland. The northern border of the district is marked by the shore of the Baltic Sea. Most of the district's communes are largely burdened by social and economic problems due to the large area of the so-called former state-owned farm areas (areas where state-owned agricultural enterprises operated until 1992).
Extension in Km ²	1,021 km ²
Number of municipalities (total)	6 municipalities: three urban-rural communes (Gryfice, Płoty, Trzebiatów), three rural communes (Brojce, Karnice, Rewal). Two communes, Rewal and Trzebiatów, due to their seaside location, are classified as tourist communes. The remaining communes: Gryfice, Brojce, Karnice, Płoty - are typically agricultural areas, once dominated by State Agricultural Farms.
Number of inhabitants (total)	56,961 inhabitants (56 persons/ km ²)

Language	Polish
Main sectors of economic activity	Companies from the trade and service sectors related to industry and construction, as well as agriculture and tourism, dominate. Economic activity in the district is concentrated in the private sector. The most popular form of running a business in the district is the sole proprietorship of a natural person.
Main vulnerable groups	Long-term unemployed, youth
MAP ACTORS	DESCRIPTION AND DATA
Number of members of the MAP (total)	20
MAP facilitator	<p>Agnieszka Kurdyś-Kujawska, PhD</p> <p>Academic lecturer at the Koszalin University of Technology, Faculty of Economic Sciences, Department of Finance. Scientific research in the field of rural and agricultural development, finances of agricultural enterprises, risk management in agriculture.</p> <p>Experience:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. MAP facilitator in the SHERPA (Sustainable Hub to Engage into Rural Policies with Actors) project. 2. MAP facilitator in the GRANULAR (Giving Rural Actors Novel data and re-Useable tools to Lead public Action in Rural areas) project. <p>Contact: agakurdys@op.pl agnieszka.kurdys-kujawska@erdn.eu</p>
MAP monitor	<p>Tomasz Aniuksztys</p> <p>Mayor of Gryfice Commune.</p> <p>President of the non-profit organisation "Stowarzyszenie Z Pomysłem".</p>

	<p>Experience:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Coach in the project "Supporting Employment Platform through Apprenticeship Learning - SEPAL" Fund for Youth Employment, following the partnership agreement concluded between the Foundation for Social and Economic Initiatives KOMES, Poland (Partner) and Bucovina Institute for Social Partnership, Romania (Partnership Leader). 2. Coordinator of the Working Group of the Association of Integrated Territorial Investments of the Gryfice Functional Area. 3. Coordinator of the CUP Koszarowa project (Koszarowa Public Service Center). "Supporting the physical, economic and social revitalization of poor communities and urban and rural areas." The project is co-financed by the European Social Fund under the Regional Operational Program of the West Pomeranian Voivodeship 2014 - 2020, Priority Axis XI, Measure 9.3. 4. Coordinator of the project "Support for people fleeing the war in Ukraine and staying in Gryfice County". The project is co-financed by the European Social Fund under the Regional Operational Program of the West Pomeranian Voivodeship 2014 - 2020, Priority Axis VII, Measure 7.6. <p>Contact: tomasz.aniuksztys@gmail.com</p>
MAP ACTORS' REPRESENTATION	DESCRIPTION AND DATA (total number)
Female participants	14
Members in the age 65+	1

Members in the age 30-	2
Public Institution members	5
Local enterprises/entrepreneurs' members by economic sector	2
Cultural and creative sector members	60% (The final number depends on the MAP participants)
Environmental associations members	5% (The final number depends on the MAP participants)
Members born in a foreign country	0
Ethnic minorities members	0
Other	0
MAP WORKING GROUPS	NUMBER OF PEOPLE IN THE GROUP
	In the case of the Polish MAP, we do not see the need to create special working groups. If necessary, we will make it.

3.1.8. Druskininkai MAP (Lithuania)

This MAP is in the Druskininkai region in southern Lithuania, near the borders with Belarus and Poland. The territory borders three rural municipalities to the north: Alytus, Lazdijai, and Varena. Druskininkai municipality comprises Druskininkai city and two rural elderships: Leipalingis and Vieciunai. The Druskininkai Local Action Group (LAG) area is sparsely populated, with a population density of 16,7 inhabitants/km² in 2021, significantly lower than Druskininkai municipality (44,3 inhabitants/km²), Alytus County (25,4 inhabitants/km²), and the national average (43,1 inhabitants/km²).

Druskininkai municipality is heavily dominated by the tourism-oriented service sector, with 69% of its territory covered by forests. Residents often collect forest products like mushrooms and berries for additional income. Agricultural land makes up only a fifth of the total area, as the soil is poor and unsuitable for farming.

The average gross salary in Druskininkai from 2014 to 2022 was lower than in both Alytus County and Lithuania, with 2022 salaries being 2,8% lower than Alytus County and 28,6% lower than the national average. Unemployment in Druskininkai decreased by 0,9%

between 2014 and 2022, but at 10,7% in 2022, it remained higher than regional (9,7%) and national (9%) rates. The municipality has a higher proportion of unemployed working-age men, attributed to a lack of business enterprises, particularly in the construction and industrial sectors.

The kick-off meeting for the Druskininkai MAP was held on 20 March 2024, focusing on "Strengthening of Social Innovations in Rural Areas" and establishing the MAP in the region. The meeting, attended by 22 participants, included mutual introductions, a presentation of the ESIRA project, and discussions on the establishment, activities, and expected outcomes of the MAP. Primary research results on challenges in the Druskininkai region were also presented and ranked. Notably, 20 participants signed informed consent forms to join the MAP for the next four years.

Table 8 Druskininkai MAP characteristics (M6)

MAP DIMENSION	DESCRIPTION AND DATA
Geographical location	Druskininkai MAP is a rural area located in the Druskininkai region, in the southern part of Lithuania, close to the border.
Extension in Km2	453,9 Km2
Number of municipalities (total)	1 municipality
Number of inhabitants (total)	19,016 inhabitants (in 2021)
Language	Lithuanian
Main sectors of economic activity	Tourism sector. Businesses and new investors are focusing on activities whose development is linked to the development of medical services, tourism and recreation, sports, and cultural events.
Main vulnerable groups	Long unemployed, older people, young, migrants (from Ukraine).
MAP ACTORS	DESCRIPTION AND DATA

Number of members of the MAP (total)	20
MAP facilitator	Alvydas Varanis, head of Druskinkai LAG. He is high motivated, good leader with experience in leading Druskinkai LAG (for 20 years). Contacts: alvydas.varanis@druskininkai.lt
MAP monitor	Agne Jazepcikaite-Gaidiene, member of Druskinkai LAG, member of Druskinkai municipality council. She is very motivated, having close relations with many NGO's, SME's in Druskininkai, participated in various projects. Contacts: vvg@druskinkai.lt
MAP ACTORS' REPRESENTATION	DESCRIPTION AND DATA (total number and %)
Female participants	14 (70%)
Members in the age 65+	2 (10%)
Members in the age 30-	2 (10%)
Public Institution members	5 (25%)
Local enterprises/entrepreneurs' members by economic sector	4 (20%)
Cultural and creative sector members	4 (20%)
Environmental associations members	0 (0%)
Members born in a foreign country	0 (0%)
Ethnic minority members	0 (0%)
Other	

MAP WORKING GROUPS	NUMBER OF PEOPLE IN THE GROUP
	One group are set in Druskininkai MAP.

3.1.9. Bodrogköz MAP (Hungary)

The expected date for the kick-off of each MAP is the beginning of July 2024 (M6). This kick-off should materialise with a MAP meeting in which the following are proposed:

- Co-evaluation of local drivers of social exclusion, the needs of population groups, the opportunities and challenges of social economy initiatives, and other contextual factors.
 - How do we gather participants' feedback during a MAP event? Directly at the MAP event, the facilitator and the monitor will use event surveys during the development of the meetings (dedicating the very last moment to fill it in). It will be short surveys orally or on paper to collect feedback from attendees. Some questions that could be interesting are related to the next:
 - What needs are most important to cover with this initiative?
 - What are your expectations with the MAP?
 - Do you think the MAP meeting adequately covers the needs?
- Co-definition of the MAPs' governance (definition of the making-decision process by the MAP) and operation as community-led innovation spaces (frequency of meetings, constitution of working groups, etc.) and of the objectives for nurturing social economy initiatives and the desired impacts through specific roadmaps prepared for each MAP.

Table 9 Bodrogköz MAP characteristics (M6)

MAP DIMENSION	DESCRIPTION AND DATA
Geographical location	Bodrogköz is a disadvantaged region in the northeast part of Hungary that is spreading to the Slovakian border.
Extension in Km2	Around 945 km ²
Number of municipalities (total)	22 municipalities

Number of inhabitants (total)	Around 20,000 inhabitants
Language	Hungarian
Main sectors of economic activity	The area is traditionally rooted in agriculture
Main vulnerable groups	Youth in NEET status. Roma people. Segregated communities.
MAP ACTORS	DESCRIPTION AND DATA
Number of members of the MAP (total)	We estimate to have 20 members in the MAP
MAP facilitator	Our MAP facilitator is Anna Szerepi, who was the leader of an MRSZA territorial development project and has a profound knowledge of the area and its social, economic and development challenges. She already set up close working relationships with local stakeholders and is an esteemed actor in the area. She is particularly interested in social innovation initiatives and the market potential of social enterprises. Tel: +36 70 286 7106, email: szerepi.anna@jobbadni.hu
MAP monitor	Our MAP monitor is Kata Vereb, who is the Deputy Chair of the Refugee Service of MRSZA. She worked with several vulnerable groups in Ireland and in Hungary, has strong project management and leadership skills and exceptional experience in community building. She is interested in social innovation processes and research methods that are capable to evaluate the efficiency of these initiatives. Tel: +36 30 164 6980 vereb.kata@jobbadni.hu
MAP ACTORS' REPRESENTATION	DESCRIPTION AND DATA (total number and %)
Female participants	3 (15%)

Members in the age 65+	1 (5%)
Members in the age 30-	2 (10%)
Public Institution members	Foreseeably 2 (10%)
Local enterprises/entrepreneurs' members by economic sector	Foreseeably 1 (5%)
Cultural and creative sector members	Foreseeably 2 (10%)
Environmental associations members	1 (5%)
Members born in a foreign country	0 (0%)
Ethnic minority members	2 (10%)
Other	
MAP WORKING GROUPS	NUMBER OF PEOPLE IN THE GROUP
Accessibility of social services and support	Since our MAP is not yet set up, it has not yet been decided if there will be working groups and, if so, which focus they will choose. We foresee three areas where social innovation is needed: 1) the accessibility of social services and support, 2) exploring the touristic potentials of the area, and 3) culture, including the cultural inheritance of the Roma as well.
Tourism	
Cultural	

4. Governance and Operational Framework of MAPs

After describing the MAPs' characteristics, it is necessary to address the potential needs that will arise in their daily operations, such as **governance and communication** issues. The characteristics of each MAP differ and identify distinct vulnerable groups within each region. However, they all share the common feature of population isolation and dispersion, which hinders the operation of the MAPs, the frequency of face-to-face meetings, and their composition, affecting both internal communication and the governance of the MAP. The following sections provide a comprehensive set of suggestions and guidelines for developing a functional and participatory way of working, which each of the nine pilots might establish in a regulations document after debating its statements with its MAP members. The objective of this guideline is to facilitate the transition towards social innovation by providing a structured framework that supports the strengthening of collective capacities and the consolidation of participatory processes. Alongside the orientation provided by specific regulatory frameworks, the guide incorporates the definition of principal roles as well as decision-making and communication strategies, which are essential for the effective functioning of these organisational structures

4.1. MAP regulations and internal organisation

Each MAP should discuss and establish all operational aspects, including governance and meeting protocols, to create a concise, clear, and effective document that will guide its work in the coming years. This document does not constitute a formal statute, but rather defines guidelines designed by the MAP for its operational and democratic governance.

Even though each MAP may decide which specific aspects to reflect in its regulations and how to define them, it is suggested that at least the following topics be addressed and specified:

- **Right to vote:** Who can participate in the MAP's decisions.
- **Voting system:** The procedures that will be used by the MAP members to vote effectively.
- **Meeting aspects:** The frequency, modality, and accessibility requirements for organising and conducting a MAP meeting.
- **Minutes:** Who will take notes during each meeting, how they will be formatted, and how they will be shared with all MAP members.

4.2. Principles of democratic governance

A MAP constitutes both a community-led innovation process and a participatory democracy platform in which all the actors involved are responsible for its decisions. This participative structure can operate in many ways, depending on the agents'

characteristics, but always aims to ensure equity and the right to vote for every person involved.

Following this premise, the next sections address various possible issues related to the democratic governance of the MAP, suggesting actions and ways of acting.

Right to vote

Addressing a democratic platform may imply a 'one person, one vote' policy, where each member can exercise an equal democratic force in the decision-making process. Nevertheless, it is also possible to have a voting system in which different stakeholders manage more votes depending on the people or collectives they represent. Each MAP should decide which procedure is more convenient and democratic for its case. Regardless of the method applied, the main goal is to ensure that all voices are heard and considered, fostering an inclusive environment where no single entity has disproportionate influence.

How to vote

It is also suggested to establish both an online voting platform and a delegate voting system to guarantee the right to vote for each person, maintain a horizontal decision-making process, and ensure equity among local agents. The online voting platform would provide easy and accessible means for all stakeholders to participate in the decision-making process, regardless of their physical location, and take into account potential MAP members with disabilities. Universal design principles should be applied to this possible online platform.

On the other hand, the delegate vote allows representatives to vote on behalf of their constituents, ensuring that the voices of larger groups are effectively represented. This process can be truly simple, for instance, using a written or digital standardised document to be completed by the person who wants to delegate their vote.

Transparency

Additionally, the platform can promote fairness and transparency, encouraging active participation and collaboration among all stakeholders. To serve this purpose, a transparency system is recommended to be implemented in which all decisions are made, and the voting processes are published. This system can be a dedicated platform, an email service, or any other mechanism allowing participants to access the minutes and other materials.

MAP roles

Apart from the proper MAP members, there are **two main roles defined in a MAP**, which will lead the cooperative decision process:

- **The Facilitator**

A person close to the territory's day-to-day life who ensures the participation of all MAP members does not interfere in the decision-making process and ensures a comfortable and safe environment. The facilitator plays a pivotal role in ensuring effective collaboration and dialogue among participants. From one side, acting as a neutral intermediary, the facilitator is responsible for structuring interactions, guiding decision-making processes, and fostering an environment of trust and inclusivity. By mediating between different perspectives and interests, the facilitator helps to translate complex issues into shared understandings, enabling participants to co-create strategies and solutions. Moreover, the facilitator ensures that communication flows remain transparent and participatory, thereby strengthening collective ownership of outcomes and enhancing the overall functionality of the MAP

- **The Monitor**

The monitor helps the facilitator in their tasks, creating safe spaces for dialogue and promoting communication and democratic standards.

Working groups

If the number of MAP members exceeds an operational size for decision-making processes, it may be advisable to create working groups. These smaller structures can discuss specific topics, debate them, and make the required decisions. For instance, these groups may be divided by thematic areas, such as productivity or rural conflict issues. Regardless of the MAP's size, it could also be recommended to create working groups if the members decide to do so.

4.3. MAP meetings

To maintain contact between local actors and establish a work rhythm in which all agents involved feel comfortable, it is suggested to organise at least one face-to-face MAP meeting with the necessary frequency to ensure the proper functioning of the MAP, and the specific intervals will be specified in the regulations of each MAP, depending on the agents' availability. Before each meeting, it is recommended that the agenda and the necessary documentation for discussion be sent to all potential participants.

During these meetings, the facilitator and the monitor may lead the discussions and potential votes, with support from other MAP members if necessary. Writing meeting minutes to summarise and reflect on the discussions and voting results conducted during each MAP or debate session is also relevant. These minutes should be public and accessible to every MAP member. It is also relevant to establish a simple and standardised system to count the attendance at meetings.

4.4. Communication

It is suggested to promote **active communication among all agents** involved in this community-led innovation process, not only among the MAP members but also with civil society and the citizens living in the MAP's area of influence. To achieve this goal, it may be relevant to differentiate between internal communication and public communication processes.

Inner communication

We call “inner communication” the messages we want to transmit to the MAP or team members. To address these agents efficiently and personally, it is suggested that the use of the most accessible and diverse communication methods possible be prioritised.

It is recommended that MAP members find the most accessible communication possible, which means prioritising and adapting messages to the app, media, or communication channel most frequently used by MAP members in each territory. Diversifying the channels used, for instance, by simultaneously using a text app, an email service, and, when required, phone calls, is also suggested.

It is important to ensure that messages are clear, direct, and personal; however, we should avoid being repetitive or insistent while maintaining regular contact with MAP members.

Also, inner communication can connect different MAPs in the ESIRA project through MAP manager and facilitator meetings and the ESIRA Community of Practice.

Public communication

We also aim to impact civil society, which involves communicating MAP progress via social media, newspapers, radio, television, and as many channels as possible. This allows the local population to understand key messages about what is happening in their territory, such as what a MAP is, the actions being developed, and how the project promotes social innovation and inclusion.

To achieve this objective, it is suggested that close contact with local media be maintained and, if possible, that they be involved in the MAP process, as they are valuable agents for rural development and social inclusion. They can make these circumstances and vulnerable groups visible to society.

4.5. Training and capacity building activities

Social inclusion and innovation processes can be challenging for many communities and local actors, including the MAP facilitators and members. To overcome this obstacle, the ESIRA project includes a train-the-trainers programme aimed at MAP facilitators and rural actors, who will be responsible for organising training activities in each MAP.

Seeking to **turn MAPs into agents of change**, and in order to facilitate the road to social innovation, the ESIRA project aims to equip its members with the necessary skills to train and strengthen the rural community through:

- **Train-the-trainers programme:** The train-the-trainers programme is one of the core activities for the effective functioning of the Multi-Actor Platforms (MAPs) and the adequate nurturing of social economy initiatives. The main objective is to develop the capacities of MAP facilitators and rural actors to promote sustainable rural development, social innovation and social economy projects and networks involving various actors such as municipalities, regional authorities, public agencies, local action groups, NGOs, and entrepreneurs. Its main goal is to enhance understanding of social inclusion for vulnerable groups, addressing significant social and economic inequalities in implementation.
 - **Training modules:** training materials incorporate theoretical concepts, practical guidelines, proposals, examples, best practices and actions designed to build competencies in critical areas such as social innovation, green transition, entrepreneurship, rural repopulation, and community engagement. Regarding the one on social innovation, given the conceptual ambiguity and evolving nature of the term, there is a pressing need for structured training programs that equip practitioners, policymakers, and community actors with a shared understanding of its principles and applications. Training serves not only to clarify definitions and frameworks but also to foster a common language that enables collaboration across disciplines and territories.
 - **Training activities:** MAP managers are targeting a minimum of 4 training sessions to equip key rural actors to drive social innovation and foster social economy initiatives. Activities must be tailored to each region and inclusive, encouraging and ensuring access for vulnerable groups to training. Each MAP should assess the feasibility of designing training activities tailored to vulnerable groups in their pilot area, adapting not only the training materials and language as needed, but also creating the most comfortable environment possible.
 - **Tailored and adapted training materials:** MAP managers are responsible for transmitting the knowledge to local actors, MAP members and vulnerable groups, generating ad-hoc materials for their needs, particularities and interests.
- **Community of Practice (CoP):** MAP managers are members of the ESIRA CoP with access to the theoretical and practical content shared on it. This community takes the form of a [LinkedIn group](#), which is very easy to join, with virtual meetings among all MAP managers to share their experiences with their respective MAPs, as

well as other face-to-face or online meetings with other stakeholders, creating cross-regional communication channels.

For instance, the MAP members will benefit from the ESIRA train-the-trainers program, which will allow them to take an active part in the formative process and promote skills and competencies for other interested stakeholders. Additionally, the MAP managers will facilitate the creation of Rural Labs at the appropriate time, providing a solid platform for nurturing social economy initiatives.

Once the central notions, processes, and ideas are clear, it might be relevant to design specific training programs tailored to the needs of social economy initiatives. For example, establishing personal and professional advising sessions, training activities tailored to social economy-specific needs, or communities of practice for mutual and significant learning and support.

One possible formative action to promote social inclusion through the MAP is the establishment of community-based workshops. These can focus on skill development, such as digital literacy, sustainable agriculture practices, and small business management. By involving residents, especially those more at risk of vulnerability such as women, youth, and older people, the MAP can create opportunities for personal and professional growth. These programs enhance individual capabilities and foster a sense of community and mutual support.

5. MAPs' Roadmaps

5.1. Purpose and structure of the MAPs' roadmaps

MAPs roadmap is a strategic view that defines **MAPs overarching objectives and the major phases and steps to achieve them**, showing how MAP's characteristics, milestones and actions connect with the ESIRA long-term outcomes. MAPs' roadmaps clarify actions that require MAP participation, ensuring that the nine ESIRA MAPs work toward the same goals despite their individual flexibility.

The structure of the MAP's roadmap include MAPs objectives and different phases of the MAP operation, including the milestones to achieve. Thus, **Phase 1** include the description of the rural ecosystem and the engagement process of MAP members and vulnerable groups, concluding with the establishment of the MAPs; **Phase 2**, which explains how the train-the-trainers programme, the training activities, and the Community of Practice must equip MAP facilitators and members to contribute to activities that build strong communities, creating the necessary environment for the MAP to become an agent of rural change through social innovation; **Phase 3**, which describe the co-designing, screening, piloting, and monitoring iterative process in Rural Labs to identify, propose, select, and support emerging social economy initiatives that sustainably contribute to the social inclusion of vulnerable groups in rural areas; and **Phase 4**, that highlight the importance of long-term viability of the MAPs and their future benefits for rural community.

5.2. MAP's objectives

The establishment of a MAP in a rural area seeks to unite and coordinate efforts to achieve a common goal in the ESIRA project: **promoting social innovation in rural contexts that pave the way for the inclusion of the most vulnerable groups**. To reach this goal, MAPs must become **a key player in social innovation facilitation in their rural area**, chasing the following objectives:

- **Facilitate the social participation** and guarantee the adequate number of members and the engagement and representativeness of the leading actors, and also the vulnerable groups in the rural area.
- **Focus on rural community social needs** to identify opportunities for the social inclusion of vulnerable groups through social economy initiatives, attending to the particularities of each pilot rural area.
- **Promote co-creation** in the rural labs, to propose, select and support social economy initiatives that contribute sustainably to the social inclusion of vulnerable groups in the rural area.

To achieve these objectives, the MAP must have a flexible structure that evolves alongside its members, becomes part of the rural community, and maintains its structure and functioning beyond the ESIRA project.

The phases of the ESIRA project determine the stages and actions of MAPs during the project (see Figure 1). By understanding these phases and steps, stakeholders can better coordinate their efforts, ensure effective communication, and achieve the MAP's overarching goals. In the following sections, it is shown how MAPs align their roles across the project phases.

Figure 2 ESIRA project plan

Source: ESIRA proposal

5.3. Phase 1. Preparing the ground: Defining MAPs

During the first months of the project (M1-M6), partners have been prepared to launch the MAPs (Multi-Actor Platforms) and investigated the challenges and opportunities of the social economy for rural inclusion. This has implied a high effort that involves researching and evaluating the context of rural marginalisation to understand the key factors that contribute to social exclusion in targeted regions. Additionally, partners have studied the existing policy frameworks addressing social inclusion and social economy initiatives to identify strengths, weaknesses, gaps, and potential synergies.

The **description of the rural ecosystem** enables better design and implementation of the MAPs while attending to the particularities of each pilot rural area and running effective governance mechanisms for different geographical contexts to enhance social innovation and the social economy in rural areas, thereby empowering vulnerable populations.

Project partners are responsible for **MAP members' engagement**, aiming for the highest representativeness (policy, civil society, academy, business and industry), collaborating with local actors to co-define their MAPs by identifying local challenges, needs, and goals, and considering gender dimensions and the participation of vulnerable groups. They will also explore how existing innovation structures, such as Local Action Groups, local associations, innovation hubs, and living labs, can be linked to and cooperate with the MAPs.

To achieve **good engagement of these vulnerable groups in the MAPs**, it is necessary to consider the following key aspects:

- **The need to build trust:** MAP managers and facilitators must carry out preliminary trust-building work to ensure the participation of the most vulnerable groups (older people, women, youth, persons with disabilities, migrants, minorities), as they may feel that their opinions will not be taken seriously, that they do not feel represented by conventional institutions, and probably do not understand the purpose of the ESIRA Project. To this end, informal meetings will be held with associations, senior centres, women's groups, or residential homes.
- **Seek mediation through credible local entities:** Organisations that already work with vulnerable groups help to explain the purpose of the ESIRA Project in an understandable way (women's associations, day centres, migrant NGOs, youth associations, or associations of people with disabilities).
- **Adapt the design of meetings:** flexible schedules that do not coincide with working or caregiving hours and that take into account transport restrictions; physical and cognitive accessibility of venues; provide transport if necessary; less formal meetings; clear, visual material in the required languages; enable online participation in dispersed territories.
- **Inclusive methodologies that avoid inequalities:** guided brainstorming, storytelling, visual cards, or world café, help to ensure quality participation.
- **Recognition of local knowledge:** publicly recognising practical local knowledge helps to empower vulnerable groups (for example, older people know a lot about the community and traditions; young people are knowledgeable about digitalisation; migrants may be familiar with new jobs).
- **Offer symbolic and material incentives to facilitate attendance:** childcare, snacks, transportation.
- **Gradual and safe participation:** small groups, practical activities such as the ones organised in the Rural Labs, oriented to specific tasks, ensure, at some point, a better engagement of the groups that are more difficult to engage at the MAPs.

The work carried out during this first phase of the project should enable the engagement of MAP members and vulnerable groups, establish MAPs, and define their governance structures, so that the MAPs are ready to start work from the sixth month onwards.

The milestones to achieve at the end of this phase are **MS1) the establishment of MAPs** and **MS2) initiation of innovation ecosystems' activities**.

5.4. Phase 2. Operating innovation ecosystems: Facilitating social innovation

One of the main ambitions of ESIRA is to explore and advance best practices for nurturing **social innovation in rural areas**. As related before, project partners must co-design and implement community-led innovation spaces in collaboration with local communities, prioritising integration with existing innovation structures.

As discussed earlier, despite its ambiguity, the notion of social innovation holds great potential in rural areas. Social innovation is, according to some authors, **“the**

reconfiguring of social practices, in response to societal challenges, which seeks to enhance outcomes on societal well-being and necessarily includes the engagement of civil society actors” (Polman et al., 2017). Therefore, **social innovation is a process of social change** characterised by the capacity to create new solutions to unmet social needs, **enabling collective action** and fostering new relationships (Sforzi et al., 2025). It is often an **iterative process**, which moves from identifying unmet needs to generating ideas, prototyping solutions, implementing pilot initiatives, and scaling up effective practices (Caulier-Grice et al., 2012).

In rural areas, communities play a leading role in collaboratively responding to increasingly complex societal challenges and co-designing novel approaches to address existing problems, serving as the core of rural social innovation (O’Shaughnessy et al., 2023). MAPs are also a representative element of the rural community with a special motivation to tackle social problems in their environment by co-designing new solutions to long-standing problems.

The composition and operating characteristics of MAPs make them **a key player in social innovation facilitation in their rural area:**

- **Ability to reconfigure social practices.** MAPs are composed of members from diverse backgrounds, thanks to the quadruple helix approach (policy, civil society, academia, and enterprises). This composition should foster new relationships, collaborations, and networks, and promote new forms and structures of governance capable of reconfiguring traditional social practices.
- **Participation of voluntary civil society actors.** MAP’s structure gives prominence to civil society in rural areas, which have traditionally been neglected and isolated. It involves voluntary civil society actors as active participants in social change. However, voluntary stakeholder engagement in MAPs ensures participants’ intrinsic interest, but it also raises questions about the operational stability of these structures.
- **Shared knowledge.** MAPs are immersed in a continuous process of learning and shared experiences that increase the ability to create new possibilities for addressing challenges and social, environmental, and economic problems in rural areas, benefiting a range of social actors, not necessarily disadvantaged groups.
- **Innovative social economy initiatives.** Social innovation could lead to organisational innovation, such as the implementation of a new organisational method, not only in the private sector but also in the public sector and hybrid public-private bodies, as well as to institutional innovation. Thanks to training, knowledge sharing, collaboration, and co-creation in rural labs, MAPs have the potential to identify, propose, select, and support social economy initiatives that sustainably contribute to the social inclusion of vulnerable groups in rural areas.

The **train-the-trainers programme**, the training activities in the MAP and the rural community, and the participation in the **Community of Practice**, must equip MAP facilitators and members to contribute to activities that **build up strong communities. Reducing social and economic inequalities contributes directly to community strengthening**, as more equal communities tend to display higher levels of social cohesion, trust, and collective capacity for action. According to the OECD (2015), lower inequalities are associated with stronger social capital, improved participation in civic life, and more resilient local economies, all of which enhance communities' ability to respond collectively to social and economic challenges.

MAP managers and facilitators are responsible for communication activities in rural areas, reinforcing and strengthening local sense of belonging, and generating new relationships and networks, including: social media groups, dissemination activities, cultural activities, one-day experiences, etc.

From this moment onwards, MAP managers, facilitators, and members are ready for the co-creation process that will take place at the Rural Lab and will have the necessary tools to identify, select, promote, and support social economy initiatives that will facilitate the inclusion of vulnerable groups in the development of their rural areas.

The milestone to achieve at the end of this phase is **MS4) the well-functioning of MAPs I** according to established criteria (M12), **MS7) the well-functioning of MAPs II** (M24), and **MS9) the well-functioning of MAPs III** (M36)

5.5. Phase 3. Rural Labs: Social innovation in progress

5.5.1. Establishment of Rural Labs

As has been anticipated throughout this deliverable, **Rural Labs are open spaces for co-creation, innovation, and experimentation**, where MAP members and facilitators put into practice the knowledge acquired through the train-the-trainers programme, the training activities and previous knowledge and experiences. The main aim of the Labs is to identify, propose, select, and support emerging **social economy initiatives** that sustainably contribute to the social inclusion of vulnerable groups in rural areas. Rural Labs aim to create a space for dialogue, participation, co-creation, learning and participatory action research to promote new innovative social inclusion initiatives in the pilot area. **Co-designing, screening, piloting, and monitoring social economy initiatives are iterative processes in Rural Labs.** Thus, taking in mind such a challenge objective, project partners and MAP managers will continuously monitor, advise and evaluate these pilot activities, assessing their benefits to the social fabric (such as job creation and improved community services), the economy (such as diversified activities and increased resilience), and the environment (such as ecosystem services and sustainable agricultural or tourism activities).

Throughout the operation of the Rural Labs, partners will employ different methodologies such as design thinking (including the well know brainstorming) and some other tools for gathering mostly qualitative data such as focus groups, conversational interviews or ethnographic observation. Some other activities similar to creative co-creation sessions with local actors), effectuation (leveraging available resources to address challenges effectively), and lean start-up principles (rapid prototyping of services, digital prototypes, piloting, and developing minimum viable products) should be also included. Once all the information is obtained, those initiatives that showi promising potential will be identified and selected for initiation and pilot testing.

By the end of the first year of the project (M12), the Rural Labs should have begun their activities and selected the **first batch of initiatives** that will be supported throughout the Project (Milestone **MS5**). To carry out this initial selection, a study of the proposed Initiatives will be conducted to understand the motivation of their promoters, the connection of the initiatives to the interests of the rural community, idea maturity, the social problem to be solved, the rural actors and vulnerable beneficiary groups involved, and the resources available to ensure their economic viability.

Additionally, new and complementary initiatives may emerge later as a result of the Rural Labs' work, benefiting from the synergies generated among them and adding to the total number of social economy initiatives the Project aims to promote.

5.5.2. Piloting social economy initiatives

An **innovative social economy initiative** is a form of economic activity that combines social or general interest objectives, economic viability and democratic or participatory governance, and that responds to rural social challenges through new or reconfigured social practices.

It prioritises people and social and/or environmental goals over profit maximisation, reinvests most surpluses for collective or general interest purposes, and actively involves civil society as a key actor in the process. By pursuing a **triple social, economic and environmental impact**, it introduces alternative ways of organising economic activities in rural areas where conventional market or public solutions are insufficient.

The piloting of social economy initiatives in ESIRA is carried out through an **accompanied, iterative, and co-creation-based process**, in which MAPs managers, facilitators, and members, together with the initiatives' promoters, work **in Rural Labs** that serve as spaces for experimentation, validation, and learning. This process includes several stages that are explained as follows. Basically, the development of social economy initiatives in rural territories requires a structured pathway that integrates mission definition, business model design, and tailored legal, technical, and financial advice. Through prototyping and validation using Lean Startup methodology, promoters can test minimum viable products

and mitigate risks before preparing a comprehensive business plan. Finally, the launch and ongoing monitoring ensure social acceptability, operational viability, and long-term impact, while providing support for scalability, replicability, and consolidation within the territory.

- **Social mission development:** social problem addressed, beneficiaries, rural change and value creation for the community.
- **Business Model Design:** Business Model Canvas will be used to design a business model that supports achieving that mission.
- **Legal, technical, and financial advice:** Specific advice will be provided based on the needs of each initiative and promoter, including guidance on the most suitable legal form for social economy, analysis of technical requirements (equipment, licences, personnel, logistics, digitalisation), and identification of potential funding sources (public funds, microfinancing, social economy instruments).
- **Prototyping (Minimum Viable Product):** It is essential to test prototypes, services, or activities in a controlled environment through Lean Startup methodology, using the minimum viable product to mitigate risks.
- **Validation** in a controlled environment.
- **Business Plan:** Once validated, a business plan must be prepared before full implementation.
- **Launch, monitoring, and ongoing support:** Continuous evaluation of the process is necessary to consider social acceptability, operational viability, potential impact, and identified barriers. Additionally, periodic feedback meetings with promoters and monitoring of social, economic, and environmental indicators will be required. Finally, support should be provided for scalability, replicability, or consolidation within the territory.

Importantly, social economy initiatives in the ESIRA framework are **not defined by their size, level of formalisation or stage of development**. They may be small-scale, emerging or early-stage initiatives, and they can operate in rural contexts with **limited institutional capacity or resources**. What defines them is not their maturity or scale, but their **social purpose**, their grounding in the territory, their commitment to social economy principles and their potential to generate social, economic and environmental value. This inclusive understanding ensures that innovative responses can emerge from diverse rural realities and that no initiative is excluded due to structural or contextual constraints.

5.5.3. Monitoring and evaluation

Monitoring and evaluation of social economy initiatives will comprise project-specific indicators and evaluation questions, as well as common ones. Project-specific indicators and evaluation questions will be determined through input from the implementers. In contrast, common indicators will be determined by taking the ESIRA project's research questions and the OECD evaluation criteria into account.

HETFFA, as the monitoring and evaluation task leader, plays a central role in developing and executing the evaluation framework, while other project partners and MAP managers contribute to data collection and analysis. Since HETFFA is not involved in delivering services within the project, it can act as an 'external' evaluator, enhancing the validity of the evaluation of project implementation and the impacts of the developed educational materials.

Data collection will be a collaborative effort. **MAP managers provide initiatives' data twice a year for monitoring.** The data are provided in digital Excel files by filling in one data sheet per region. The data should be sent to HÉTFA by the schedule as follows: 30 April 2025, 30 October 2025, 30 April 2026, 30 October 2026, 30 April 2027

The monitoring activity will feed into the evaluation's data requirements, as well as into 3 monitoring reports (in M12, M24, and M36). These reports will be shared with the MAP managers, who will be able to plan action when a significant deviation from the project-specific and common objectives is detected.

The evaluation should mainly focus on the viability of supported social economy initiatives, with the assessment indicating positive or promising viability based on relevant indicators, **which must achieve the following criteria:**

- Number of social economy initiatives initiated and supported during the project duration: **50 new initiatives.**
- Viability ratio to achieve at the end of the project (2027) and the two years following (2028-2030): **50% viability ratio** (a total of 25 initiatives).

The evaluation process will show the adequate nurturing of social economy initiatives and the achievement of **milestones MS5, MS8, and MS10**, in M12, M24, and M36, respectively.

5.6. Phase 4. Long-term viability of MAPs

Once the project is completed, it is essential to reflect on how to build on the potential of the MAPs for future initiatives. It is essential to recognise that the **MAPs are not merely a project structure but a collaborative governance framework** that, through inclusive participation and strategic alignment, enhances the sustainability and impact of social innovation in rural contexts. The MAPs bring together rural actors who have developed trust, shared a common agenda, and learned to work collaboratively throughout ESIRA. It would be a missed opportunity to let these relationships and this working culture dissolve once the formal project ends. Instead, the **MAPs can serve as a long-term asset**—an established ecosystem that can be activated, expanded, and mobilised in new projects, policy processes, or community-led initiatives.

Maintaining and leveraging the MAPs beyond ESIRA can generate several benefits:

- **Sustaining collaborative governance:** The MAPs have created a space for dialogue between public authorities, community organisations, researchers, and social economy actors. This multi-actor governance approach can continue to support decision-making and territorial development.
- **Supporting new proposals and funding opportunities:** A functioning MAP provides an organised structure for co-designing and validating ideas, which makes it easier to generate competitive proposals for new Horizon Europe calls, Interreg projects, or national and regional programmes.
- **Ensuring continuity of social innovation processes:** The MAPs have already identified local needs, opportunities, and working groups. Building on this knowledge increases the likelihood that the Rural Labs or pilot initiatives will continue evolving and scaling.
- **Strengthening local ecosystems:** The MAPs can evolve into permanent innovation ecosystems that support ongoing initiatives in areas such as social entrepreneurship, community services, green transition, digital inclusion, or youth empowerment.
- **Institutionalising participation:** The MAP model can inspire or be integrated into municipal or regional governance frameworks, creating formal or semi-formal structures for citizen engagement and co-creation.

To make this possible, project partners and local actors should consider how to maintain MAP engagement after ESIRA—whether through local ownership, integration in public strategies, collaboration agreements, or the creation of a light structural framework that allows MAPs to remain active with minimal resources. In this way, the MAPs become not only a tool for ESIRA, but a lasting mechanism for supporting rural development and social innovation in the long term.

Consortium will also focus on the long-term sustainability of MAPs developed in the pilot rural areas beyond the project's duration. It will explore specific plans for replicating successful models that nurture social economy practices in similar regions. By strategically drafting replicability plans, the project aims to establish a framework for sustaining and scaling social innovation efforts in rural areas. This approach ensures that the insights gained and methodologies tested during the project can be effectively applied elsewhere, contributing to broader efforts to reduce rural marginalisation and support inclusive economic development.

From a policy perspective, ensuring the continuity of the MAPs beyond the lifetime of ESIRA is essential to consolidate their value as local governance and innovation structures. Policymakers at local, regional and national levels should consider integrating MAPs into existing rural development frameworks, providing light and flexible institutional support that allows these platforms to continue facilitating collaboration between public authorities, civil society and social economy actors. This may include recognising MAPs within participatory governance strategies, allocating modest but stable resources for coordination, and enabling MAPs to contribute to policy design and implementation. By doing so, governments can harness the **MAPs as long-term mechanisms** for strengthening rural innovation ecosystems, improving policy responsiveness, and ensuring that social economy initiatives remain embedded in community needs and capacities.

The milestone to achieve at the end of the project is **MS11) Long-term viability of project's MAPs** in M42.

6. Summary and risk mitigations

ESIRA MAPs are a social structure of the rural communities led in the project. Thanks to the composition and operating characteristics of the nine ESIRA MAPs, described in the previous sections, they are **key players in facilitating social innovation** in their rural areas, due to **1)** their ability to foster new relationships, collaborations, and networks, and promote new forms and structures of governance capable of **reconfiguring traditional social practices**; **2)** the participation of **voluntary civil society actors**; **3)** the generation of **shared knowledge** that increase the ability to create new possibilities for addressing challenges and social, environmental, and economic problems in rural areas; and **4)** their potential to identify, propose, select, and support **social economy initiatives** that sustainably contribute to the social inclusion of the identified vulnerable groups in rural areas through Rural Labs.

As emphasised across this Derivable, within the structure of the MAPs, Rural Labs are conceived as experimental and participatory spaces that bring strategic reflection into territorial practice. While the MAP provides the governance framework and facilitates articulation among diverse actors—institutions, local communities, the private sector, and civil society—the Rural Lab functions as an operational environment where initiatives of social innovation are designed, prototyped, and validated according to rural need. **Rural Labs are designed as open spaces for co-creation, innovation, and experimentation**, where MAP members and facilitators can put into practice the knowledge acquired through the train-the-trainers programme and training activities to identify, propose, select, and support emerging **social economy initiatives** that sustainably contribute to the social inclusion of vulnerable groups in rural areas.

This MAPs roadmap is a strategic view that defines MAP's overarching objectives and the major phases and steps to achieve them, showing how MAP's characteristics, milestones and actions connect with the ESIRA long-term outcomes.

However, eleven potential critical risks were identified in the ESIRA proposal that could affect the functioning of MAPs across the different roadmap phases. From these eleven critical risks, the following ones are directly related to MAPs' establishment and functioning:

- **Risk 3:** Low facilitation skills of MAP facilitators.

Mitigation measure: To reduce this threat, the train-the-trainers programme will provide training and mentoring to support facilitators in their work. Continuing monitoring of MAP activities will provide immediate feedback so additional materials and support can be provided throughout the project.

Risk 4: Low interest and engagement of MAP members. MAPs characteristics show the lack of engagement of some groups in some pilots (youth under 30). The

voluntary engagement of stakeholders in MAPs and community-led innovation spaces ensures participants' intrinsic interest, but it also raises questions about the operational stability of these structures. Financial incentives are a controversial issue. The ESIRA MAP framework promotes non-material incentives and voluntary participation, considering training, events, workshops, and relationships as key drivers.

Mitigation measure: The analysis of specific needs will be done to identify relevant topics for MAP activities and the invitation of relevant stakeholder groups, trying to increase the attractiveness of being part of the MAP. For instance, Pinares Burgos-Soria MAP has designed a specific training programme for young people in order to engage this group to the MAP activities. The initiative has been quite successful, and almost 10 young people from the rural area have taken part in this project, identifying three new social economy initiatives for ESIRA support.

- **Risk 7:** Lack of motivation and social, economic and institutional organisational structure to give continuity to the project in the rural territory once the project has ended.

Mitigation measure: Establishment of community links between the entities participating in the project, the social, economic and institutional agents of the territory (design of a collaborative network).

- **Risk 8:** Lack of training and experience of the social, economic and institutional actors of the territory to efficiently and rapidly implement the proposed social economy initiatives.

Mitigation measure: Design training pills or micro-credentials, as well as experimental workshops, to cover the training needs of the rural actors to execute the initiatives.

- **Risk 10:** Social economy innovative initiatives initiated throughout the project cannot take place.

Mitigation measure: Project partners have enough experience in field activities and a wide network of stakeholders to develop the initiatives.

- **Risk 11:** Lack of involvement of vulnerable groups. MAPs' characteristics indicate a lack of engagement among some vulnerable groups in some pilots (for example, migrants).

Mitigation measure: Each partner will establish an agreement with local NGOs and associations to ensure participation of this group. Also, specific communication activities will be carried out. Some MAPs have already established communications with local NGOs to carry out activities with minority groups (Hungarian MAP).

The project partners will be continuously warning of the potential risks to implement mitigation measures as soon as possible.

Figure 3 presents a visual infography of the MAPs roadmap (objectives, phases, risks).

Figure 3 ESIRA MAPs roadmap

Source: Own elaboration

7. References

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8. Partners

